

Impact of Motivation on the Performance of Employees of NCR

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Abstract: Since motivation has been a key indicator of how well employees do their jobs for a long time, organisations and human resource managers have been very concerned about it. There are a lot of things that have to do with management, employees, the organization, and the workplace, which makes it hard and complicated to get people to work hard. So, the organization and the person in charge of human resources should use a variety of strategies and methods to get people to work hard. When a person joins a company, they have to meet different needs and meet different expectations. Human resource managers use both monetary and non-monetary factors to reach different goals for employees and the organization as a whole. Employee motivation can be regarded of as a force that drives employees toward the attainment of specific organizational goals and aims. These days, it is one of the most contentious issues in businesses, as every company strives to make the most efficient use possible of both its financial and human resources. The primary objectives of this research are to examine the kinds of factors that have an impact on employee motivation in NCR and to determine the extent to which motivation influences employee performance. A questionnaire that is self-administered is used to collect data from 200 teachers who work in government schools as well as private schools. In order to determine the effect that employee motivation has on employee performance, regression analysis is used. This study takes into account four variables: employee motivation; employee performance; intrinsic rewards; and employee perceived training effectiveness. The findings of this research indicate that there is a considerable and favorable relationship between the motivation of employees and the performance of such employees. Furthermore, this study came to the conclusion that a substantial positive relationship exists between intrinsic rewards and employee performance as well as employee motivation. According to the findings of this study, an employee's perception of the effectiveness of training has a negative correlation with their level of motivation. It is also proven from their comments that although they were provided with the training courses, they did not utilise this training in their routine teaching because they believed it to be unproductive. This can be proven from both of these aspects. The fact that they were dissatisfied with the training that was offered to them had a negative impact on their motivation to teach.

Key words: Employee Motivation, Employee Performance, Intrinsic Rewards, Employee Perceived Effectiveness.

Introduction

Motivation is derived from the word 'motive,' which refers to an individual's needs, desires, wants, or urges. It is the process of motivating individuals to take action in order to attain a goal. Need for Money, Respect, Job Satisfaction, Accomplishment, etc., might be among the psychological variables motivating people's actions in the context of their work goals. Motivation plays a vital role in the management process as a whole. This strategy is effective for encouraging employees to contribute positively to the achievement of company goals. Motivation is required because human nature necessitates some form of inducement, encouragement, or incentive for improved performance.

Employees are motivated by the following factors:

- Ask workers what they want
- Ask workers what they want
- Treating employees with respect
- Treating employees with respect

- Feedback and training from managers and leaders
 - Industry-standard benefits and remuneration
 - Carry a notebook for ideas
 - Explain the incentive system
- Motivate people to enjoy hard work. Today's workers must know why they're toiling. Every employee is driven differently. Employee motivation is a company's workers' degree of energy, devotion, and innovation. Managers get work done through staff. Managers must motivate staff to do this. Not so easy! Motivation is a multidisciplinary subject. Despite vast basic and applied research, motivation is poorly understood and implemented. Motivation requires understanding human nature. Problem! Man is simple yet complex. Understanding and appreciating this is necessary for effective staff motivation, management, and leadership. Every concern demands physical, financial, and mental motivation from employees and human resources to reach goals. Motivation maximises human resources. Building

employee work ethic helps. This helps the company maximise resource use. It increases productivity, reduces costs, and improves efficiency. Motivated co-ordination and cooperation can achieve goals. Stability of staff is vital for a company's reputation and goodwill. Only when employees feel like they're part of the management will they remain loyal. Employees' talents and efficiency benefit both employers and workers. This will lead to a good market image, which will attract skilled employees. In the context of today's globalised environment, businesses are continually looking for ways to improve the skills of their employees and to inspire them through the use of HR software and procedures. According to Güngör (2011), businesses will not succeed until they implement reward management. According to Barber and Bertz (2000), incentive management enables companies to better attract, retain, and motivate high-potential employees, which ultimately leads to improved business results. Money and bonuses are examples of extrinsic benefits, whereas recognition, security, a title, promotion, appreciation, praise, participation in decision-making, flexible working hours, workplace comfort abilities, feedback, work design, social rights, and other intrinsic rewards are examples of intrinsic benefits. Extrinsic benefits include things like money and bonuses (Yang, 2008). According to Grant, levels of motivation have an effect on staff performance and productivity (2008). According to what he discovered, motivated workers are more self-driven and respect autonomy. People that are motivated to work are interested in what they do and are eager to accept responsibility (Kuvaas & Dysvik, 2009).

The formalised process of obtaining new knowledge, skills, and capabilities is referred to as training. The orientation and magnitude of one's efforts, as well as the psychological quality that stirs an organism to motion, are both referred to as motivation. Training tactics have an effect on the motivation of employees as well as the commitment of organisations (Meyer & Allen, 1991). Rowden and Conine (2005) state that training leads to an increase in employee work satisfaction, which in turn leads to an increase in customer performance. Employees that are committed to learning report higher levels of happiness and have greater overall performance (Tsai et al, 2007). Tsai et al. (2007) and Harrison (2000) both

agree that training that is prompted by learning helps increase employee performance and is essential to the accomplishment of organisational goals (Harrison, 2000). According to the findings of the study, the performance of a company is determined by a variety of elements, the most important of which is the level of employee motivation (Saif ullah malik et al., 2012).

Intrinsic rewards are intangible awards of recognition or achieving motivation in any work when one sees in Maslow's hierarchy as conscious fulfilment. In other words, intrinsic rewards are motivation that comes from inside. It's having the satisfaction of knowing you did something positive or brightened someone else's day. Employees are encouraged through the use of incentive management systems, particularly intrinsic rewards, which affect both individual and organisational performance. Both Pool and Pool (2007) and Lok and Crawford (2004) feel that there is a connection between motivation and job satisfaction. According to Tsai et al research,

there is a considerable connection can be found between perceived training effectiveness and job satisfaction (2007).

Models and theories concerning motivation can be found in the field of organisational behaviour. Concentrate on the professional development of your staff. Progress is considered to be the most important factor in employee motivation by Maslow, Alderfer, McClelland, Hackman, and Herzberg. [Citations needed] There is a connection between employee motivation, work satisfaction, and organisational commitment (Basset-Jones and Lloyd, 2005; Chen et al., 2004). The success of any organisation, whether public or private, is directly correlated to the level of employee motivation (Chintallo & Mahadeo, 2013).

According to the findings of a study that was conducted by Sirota et al. (2005) with the participation of 135,000 respondents from a variety of different groups and countries, businesses that implemented motivation programmes that involved camaraderie, equity, and achievement were more successful than businesses that either had no employees or twice as many employees who were enthusiastic (of total 45 percent). According to the findings of a study, the productivity of workers improves when they experience higher levels of motivation (Asim, 2013).

Intrinsic reward

Intrinsic motivation is an interest in the activity itself rather than external influences and incentives. Organizations need something to keep their staff working, such as salary or bonuses, but motivation is highly vital to keep workers engaged and involved in their work so that their quality and quantity of work and productivity doesn't decline (Williams, 2004). Intrinsic reward is the enjoyment a person gets from working in a good organisation that compensates him for his work. Employees value extrinsic and intrinsic rewards. Intrinsic motivation comes from within (pleasure, satisfaction, pride) while extrinsic incentive comes from outside (salary, money, grades, etc). (Scott and Bruce, 1994),.

Intrinsically driven people work on math problems because they're entertaining or they're tough and provide them pleasure to solve. In both circumstances, extrinsic rewards such as payment or award are unimportant (Roberts, 1991 and Rothwell, 1992). It doesn't imply extrinsic incentive isn't necessary, but it's not enough to motivate someone (Eisenberger and Cameron, 1996; Janssen, 2000; Mumford, 2000).

A study indicated that rewards are key to reducing employee unhappiness. When employees are happy, they work harder and with more interest, leading to good performance (Mehmod, 2013). Intrinsic rewards influence employee performance, according to a study. When individuals receive intrinsic rewards, they realise their performance and work harder to be recognised. (2014)

Importance of Motivation

The concept of motivation holds a great place and function throughout the entirety of the management process. Encouragement of workers to make a constructive contribution to the accomplishment of organisational goals is a beneficial use of this strategy, which can be employed fruitfully. Because of the nature of the human race, individuals typically require some form of induction, encouragement, or incentive in order to achieve higher levels of performance. This points to the significance of providing incentives to workers. Increasing an employee's sense of motivation is one way to boost their performance, even if they are working at a lower level.

Along with their other responsibilities, managers are expected to fulfil the role of employee motivator as part of their job description. It is necessary for a manager to act

not only as a friend but also as a motivator to the people under his supervision. The ability to stay motivated is beneficial in all facets of life, including the interactions we have with our family. The situation is exactly the same in business. This strongly shows that having a motivated attitude is quite crucial. It is an integral component of the management process overall.

When it comes to getting employees excited about their jobs, management can put a powerful tool at their disposal: motivation. When employees are motivated, they are more inclined to put in effort at work, which ultimately leads to an increase in the efficiency of the firm.

Better usage of available resources; decreased incidence of labour issues; substantial gains in production and productivity; enhanced public perception

Objectives of the Study

To study the significant and positive relationship of Employee motivation with employee performance.

To study the significant and positive relationship of intrinsic reward with employee performance.

To study the significant and positive relationship of intrinsic reward with employee motivation.

To study the significant and positive relationship of Employee perceived training effectiveness with employee motivation.

Hypotheses of the Study

There has a significant and positive relationship of Employee motivation with employee performance.

There has a significant and positive relationship of intrinsic reward with employee performance.

There has a significant and positive relationship of intrinsic reward with employee motivation.

There has a significant and positive relationship of Employee perceived training effectiveness with employee motivation.

Research Methodology

This method of research is known as descriptive research, which implies describing and explaining a specific explanation. The focus of the descriptive research is on describing the current condition, rather than making evaluations or offering interpretations of the present situation (Creswell, 1994). Verifying the hypothesis that accurately reflects the current condition is one of the main focuses of the present situation.

Sampling Data

The population of this study consists of the faculty members of Government and private schools of NCR. A sample of 200 respondents were asked to complete a questionnaire. This study used convenience sampling, which is a non-probability sampling technique. Convenience sampling entails the gathering and collection of information and data from the sample of the study or the unit in the study that are easily accessible and convenient.

Instruments of the Present Study

There are two major objectives of the present study regarding survey instruments: The first is the relationship between various variables in the implementation of employee motivation. Second, it can be used to collect information on respondents with diverse characteristics in order to comprehend the variations. The survey of instruments has 2 parts.

Part 1 contains various individual and demographic factors. This part will collect information regarding the respondent's gender, age, income, and level of education.

The importance of Part ii in the current study cannot be emphasized. These variables consist of employee motivation, performance, intrinsic reward, and perceived training efficacy. This component of the study is based on previously utilized questionnaires and previous material. The study's scale was derived from previous research and published literature.

Procedure

The questionnaire was distributed to 200 NCR-based respondents. Before administering the questionnaire, the respondents were briefed on the goal of the study and the questions so that they could easily provide pertinent responses. 200 questionnaires were selected in total. After questionnaires were collected, they were categorized and placed into an SPSS sheet for further analysis.

Results and Interpretation:

After the prerequisites for reliability and validity have been met, this portion of the study tests the model. On dependent variables, the casual associations of the independent variable are measured. Motivation and Performance of Employees With (Beta=0.373) and ($p < 0.01$), the study's regression findings indicate the considerable positive relationship between Employee motivation and Employee performance. According to these findings, employee motivation exceeds employee

performance by 45%. The study's results support hypothesis 1.

Intrinsic reward and Employee Performance The employee motivation model's regression analysis suggests a significant positive relationship between (Beta=0.185) and ($p < 0.01$). The results indicate that intrinsic reward is approximately 21% greater than Employee performance. The study's results support hypothesis 2.

Intrinsic Motivation and Employee Reward

Employee motivation has a significant positive relationship with the variable intrinsic reward, according to the study's findings. This variable has a statistically significant positive correlation with (Beta=0.310) and ($p < 0.01$). This indicates that intrinsic rewards contribute more than 52% to employee motivation. The results of the present study confirm the hypothesis 3.

Employee perceptions of the effectiveness of training and Employee motivation

The study's regression results (Beta=-0.003 and $p > 0.01$) confirm the negative relationship between employees' perceptions of training effectiveness and employee motivation. According to these findings, training efficacy as viewed by employees contributes more than 5% to employee motivation. This study's result does not validate hypothesis 4.

Discussion

This research explores the relationship between employee motivation, performance, and perceived training efficacy. It encourages employee motivation. Business-to-business (B2B) employees said they were motivated by their autonomy, independence, responsibility, and position and tasks from management. Some respondents said art, design, or architecture could be motivational, but they didn't say for sure. Respondents said these three constructs boost employee engagement by improving the physical work environment. Improving the working environment improves employee well-being, emotions, and encouragement, which increases motivation. Some respondents disagreed since they weren't interested in the physical environment. Employee motivation, performance, intrinsic reward, and perceived training efficacy are relevant variables. Multi-item questionnaires based on empirical research were employed to measure these characteristics. The study used teacher data. According to their comments, they were given training courses but didn't use them in their everyday teaching because they were unsuccessful. Unsatisfactory training

reduced their motivation to teach.

Bibliography

1. Ameer-ul-Ameer & Hanif, F., 2013. Impact of Training on Employee's Development and Performance in Hotel Industry of Lahore, Pakistan. *Journal of Business Studies Quarterly*, Volume 4, pp. 68-82.
2. Asim, M., 2013. impact of motivation on employee performance with the effect of training: specific to education sector of pakistan. *international journal of scientific and research publications*, Volume 3, pp. 1-9.
3. Agwu, M.O., (2013) Impact of Fair Reward System on Employees Job Performance in Nigerian Agip Oil Company Limited Port-Harcourt, *British Journal of Education, Society & Behavioral Science*, 3(1), pp 47-64. Ahmad, M. B., Wasay, E., & Malik, S.
4. U. (2012). Impact of Employee Motivation on Customer Satisfaction: Study of Airline Industry in Pakistan, *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business*, 4(6), 531-539.
5. Azar, Alderfer, C. (1972), Existence, Relatedness and Growth: Human Needs in Organizational Settings, *Free Press, New York, NY*.
6. Barber, A.E., Dunham, R. and Formisano, R.A. (1992), "The impact of flexible benefits on Employee satisfaction: a field study", *Personnel Psychology*, Vol. 45, pp. 55-75.
7. Basset-Jones, N. and Lloyd, G.F. (2005), "Does Herzberg's motivation theory have staying power?", *The Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 24, pp. 929-43
8. Chen, Y., Lou, H., 2002. Toward an understanding of the behavioral intention to use a groupware application.
9. Chiaburu, D.S. and Tekleab, A.G. (2005), "Individual and contextual influences on multiple Dimensions of training effectiveness", *Journal of European Industrial Training*, Vol. 29 No. 8, pp. 604-26. Chintaloo, S & Mahadeo, J. (2013). Effect of Motivation on Employees' Work Performance at Ireland Blyth Limited: *Proceedings of 8th Annual London Business Research Conference Imperial College, London, UK*, 8 ISBN: 978-1-922069-28-3.
11. Deci, E.L. and Ryan, R.M. (2000), "The 'what' and 'why' of goal pursuits: human needs and the self-determination of behaviour", *Psychological Inquiry*, Vol. 11 No. 4, pp. 227-68 Lovelock, C.H. (1996), *Services Marketing*, Prentice-Hall.
12. Edirisooriyaa, W. A., 2014. Impact of Rewards on Employee Performance: With Special Reference to ElectricCo..
13. *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Management and Economics*, pp. 311-318.
14. Greenwich, CT. Ryan, R.M. and Deci, E.L. (2000), "Intrinsic and extrinsic motivations: classic definitions and new directions", *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, Vol. 25 No. 1, pp. 54-67.
15. Harrison, R. (2000), *Employee Development*, Beekman Publishing, Silver Lakes, Pretoria. Pool, S. and Pool, B. (2007), "A management development model", *Journal of Management Development*, Vol. 26 No. 4, pp. 353-69. Kuvaas, B. and Dysvik, A. (2009), "Perceived investment in Employee Development, intrinsic Motivation and Work Performance", *Human Resource Management Journal*, 19(3), pp. 217-236
16. Kanelopoulos, C. and Akrivos, C. (2006), "Career development in Greek management", *Spoudai*, Vol. 56 No. 1, pp. 79-106.
17. Meyer, J. and Allen, N. (1991), "A three component conceptualization of organizational commitment", *Human Resource Management Review*, Vol. 1 No. 1, pp. 61-90.
18. M & Shafiqhi, A. (2013). The Effect of Work Motivation on Employees' Job Performance: *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, Vol. 3, No. 9 ISSN: 2222-6990.
20. Rowden, R.W. and Conine, C.T. Jr (2005), "The impact of workplace learning and job satisfaction in small US commercial banks", *Journal of workplace Learning*, Vol. 17 No. 4, pp. 215-30.
21. Satisfaction: Study of Airline Industry in Pakistan: *Interdisciplinary Journal of Contemporary Research in Business, Institute of Interdisciplinary Business Research*, Vol. 4, No. 6.
22. Tsai, P., Yen, C.Y., Huang, L. and Huang, I. (2007), "A study on motivating employee's learning commitment in the post-downsizing era: job satisfaction perspective", *Journal of World Business*, Vol. 42 No. 2, pp. 157-69.
23. Vansteenkiste, M., Lens, W. and Deci, E.L. (2006), "Intrinsic versus extrinsic goal contents in self-determination theory: another look at the quality of academic motivation", *Educational Psychologist*, Vol.

- 41 No. 1, pp. 19-31.
24. Yang, H. (2008), ‘Efficiency Wages and Subjective Performance Pay’, *Economic Inquiry*, 46(2), pp. 179–196.
 25. Yazıcı, N. K., ‘the Effect of Reward System Applications on Employee Performance In Service Sector’, (2008), *Marmara University, Institute of Social Sciences, Master Thesis.*